

block design with three replications (Table 1). Potash was applied per treatment in two equal splits as basal and 30 d after transplanting (DT) (panicle initiation stage); K₂O as basal at 50 kg ha⁻¹; and N at 125 kg ha⁻¹ with 50 kg ha⁻¹ as basal and 25 kg ha⁻¹ on 15, 30, and 45 DT. Grain yield was assessed by plot, and yield component traits were recorded on five plants in a single replication.

Significant differences were found between the levels of K, lime, and their interaction. At all K levels, lime application increased grain yield. Application at 75 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ with lime resulted in the highest grain yield of 6.5 t ha⁻¹.

Without lime application, K response was low and at 125 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ the grain yield was only 5.5 t ha⁻¹ (Table 1). Increases were also observed in plant height, productive tillers, panicle length, filled grains panicle⁻¹, and 1000-grain weight (Table 2).

Potassium is an excellent replacer of Al in exchangeable clay complexes. Soluble Al (hindrance to P uptake) is precipitated into aluminum hydroxide by the application of lime, which mitigates the toxic effect of Al and increases the uptake of K in acid soils. In these acid soils, 75 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ applied with 2.8 t lime ha⁻¹ were optimum for rice cultivation. ■

Table 2. Effect of K and lime application on plant characters of rice grown on acid soil.^a

K ₂ O (kg ha ⁻¹)	Plant height (cm)		Productive tillers hill ⁻¹ (no.)		Panicle length (cm)		Filled grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)		1000-grain weight(g)	
	L0 ^b	L1 ^b	L0	L1	L0	L1	L0	L1	L0	L1
	0	80	82	6.1	6.3	18	20	57	64	21.0
25	80	83	6.2*	6.5	20	21	80	81	21.0	21.5
50	81	83	5.9	6.8	20	21	84	87	21.6	22.0
75	82*	88*	6.2*	6.8	21*	22*	89	97*	21.8	22.1
100	81	89*	6.2*	6.9*	21*	22*	93*	106*	22.0*	22.1
125	83*	92*	6.2*	6.9*	21*	22*	104*	106*	22.0	22.6*

^a * = significant at the 5% level. ^b L0 = zero lime, L1 = lime at 2.8 t ha⁻¹

Increased yield of lowland rice with late N application in the reproductive phase and at high N rates

P. C. Pandey, P. S. Bisht, and P. Lal, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, Nainital, Uttar Pradesh, India

Nitrogen deficiency results from current recommendations of local best-split N applications. A field experiment was designed to test the hypothesis that supplying a large proportion of N during the reproductive phase (1 wk before panicle initiation, at booting, and at heading) would eliminate this deficiency and improve yields. Applications at recommended N (120 kg ha⁻¹) and at an increased level (180 kg N ha⁻¹)

were carried out in a split-plot design (N rates in main plots and N splits in subplots). The experiments used four replications during the wet seasons of 1988, 1989, 1991, and 1992 at Pantnagar (29° N, 79° E, and 244 m) on silt loam with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, CEC 20 meq 100 g⁻¹ soil, 0.1% total N, 13.9 kg available P (Olsen) ha⁻¹, and 202 kg available K ha⁻¹ (NH₄OAc extraction). Rice variety Pant Dhan 4 (134 d duration) was sown 1 Jun in a nursery and transplanted between 5 and 15 Jul in the 4 yr with basal applications of 18 kg P ha⁻¹, 33 kg K ha⁻¹, and 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹.

Time of N application had a significant effect in all years except 1989 (Table 1). In general, the results suggest that controlling the supply of N during initial growth stages and following

Table 1. Effect of N applications on grain yield of rice.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)				Mean
	1988	1989	1991	1992	
<i>N rate (kg ha⁻¹)</i>					
120	6.7	7.0	5.2	7.4	6.6
180	7.2	7.7	6.7	7.7	7.3
LSD (0.05)	0.4	0.7	0.7	0.3	
<i>Time of N application^a</i>					
T1	6.5	7.2	6.0	7.3	6.8
T2	6.7	7.3	—	—	7.0
T3	17.4	7.4	6.2	7.8	7.2
T4	7.2	7.4	5.8	8.0	7.1
T5	7.2	7.4	—	—	7.3
T6	6.7	7.4	—	—	7.1
T7	—	7.5	5.8	7.4	6.9
LSD (0.05)	0.5	ns	0.4	0.5	
Interaction	ns	ns	ns	ns	
CV (%)	6	7	5	5	

^a T1 = 1/2 basal, 1/4 at tillering, 1/4 at 6-7 d before panicle initiation (DBPI); T2 = 2/3 basal, 1/3 at 6-7 DBPI; T3 = 1/5 basal, 1/5 at tillering, 1/5 at 6-7 DBPI, 1/5 at booting, 1/5 at heading; T4 = 1/5 basal, 1/5 at tillering, 1/5 at 6-7 DBPI, 1/5 at booting, 1/5 (foliar spray) at heading; T5 = 1/4 basal, 1/4 at tillering, 1/6 at 6-7 DBPI, 1/6 at booting, 1/6 at heading; T6 = 1/4 basal, 1/4 at tillering, 1/6 at 6-7 DBPI, 1/6 at booting, 1/6 (foliar spray) at heading; T7 = 1/2 basal, 1/8 at tillering, 1/8 at 6-7 DBPI, 1/8 at booting, 1/8 at heading.

Table 2. Economics of late N application at booting and heading stages over recommended N split application at two N rates.^a

Economic factor	N rates (kg ha ⁻¹)	
	120	180
1. Added labor for topdressing of urea per ha required at booting and heading	1	1
2. Wage of labor (US\$ d ⁻¹)	1.2	1.2
3. Added labor cost (US\$)	1.2	1.2
4. Added yield of rice obtained from late application (t ha ⁻¹)	0.5	0.4
5. Price of rice (US\$ t ⁻¹)	100	100
6. Added return (US\$)	50	40
7. Added net return from late application (item 6-item 3)	48.8	38.8

^aCost of cultivation was the same for both treatments except for the extra cost incurred in topdressing of urea at booting and heading. Av of 1988, 1989, 1991, and 1992 data.

with applications of larger amounts of N topdressing in the reproductive stages bring higher yields than the recommended N split application.

Based on added return-added cost ratio, topdressing N at late stages (booting and heading) would be more profitable over the recommended N split (Table 2). Late application at booting and heading at 120 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹ gave an additional return of

US\$48.80 and US\$38.80, respectively, over the recommended N split (T1).

This study also found a significant response of rice after applications of 180 kg N ha⁻¹ in all years (Table 1). The grain yield over 120 kg N ha⁻¹ was 0.5 t in 1988, 0.7 t in 1989, 1.5 t in 1991, and 0.3 t in

1992, or an average increase of 0.75 t. With the present cost of fertilizer and price of rice, the net return is US\$62.40 ha⁻¹. Thus economic doses of N for transplanted rice now reach as high as 180 kg N ha⁻¹ in intensive cropping in the Tarai region of Uttar Pradesh, India. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Management of urea briquettes containing diammonium phosphate increases rice yields of small farmers

S. Y. Daftardar, Janaseva Foundation, Dadra, 296230 Union Territory of DNH, India; S. M. Wagle, Bharatiya AgroIndustries Foundation, Jwhar, 401603 Thane District, Maharashtra, India; and N. K. Savant, StaSav International, 2551 Hough Road, Florence, AL, 35630, USA

We compared the use of conventional prilled urea (PU), diammonium phosphate (DAP), and urea briquettes (UB) containing DAP (UB-DAP)(4:1, N:P) as NP sources for rainfed transplanted rice. The experiments were done in the 1993, 1994, and 1995 wet seasons in a warm subhumid tropical region on the west coast of Maharashtra State, India.

Three regimes were tested in 117 farmer-managed field trials: (1) Improved management. The UB-DAP was deep-placed by hand on the day of transplanting (DP) with modified 20 × 20-cm spacing (see figure). One 2.7-g UB-DAP per 4 hills supplied 56 kg N ha⁻¹ and 14 kg P ha⁻¹. (2) Conventional management. Nitrogen as PU was applied in two splits (one-half at DP and one-half topdressed at panicle initiation stage) and all P as single superphosphate (SSP) at DP was applied at the same N and P rates as that in improved and farmers' management. (3) Farmers' management. Traditional random transplanting and fertilizer at 0-40 kg N ha⁻¹ and 0-10 kg P ha⁻¹.

Average plot size was about 100 m². Duration of rice cultivars ranged from

110 to 135 d. Four- to five-week-old seedlings, prepared by farmers, were transplanted at 5-6 seedlings hill⁻¹ for the improved management trial. Value-cost ratio (VCR) of fertilizer management was determined by dividing the value of additional grain + straw yields by all additional variable costs of fertilizers and their application. First-degree stochastic dominance analysis was used to determine risk efficiency.

Despite marked differences in seasonal rainfall, improved management significantly increased grain and straw yields over conventional management (PU + SSP) and was distinctly superior to farmers' management (see table). Agronomic performance of PU + SSP was variable and unsatisfactory. Yields for improved management with improved varieties needed 40% less

a) Bamboo transplanting guide method; b) Two-row transplanting method used for achieving the modified 20×20 cm spacing (plant population, 25 hills m⁻²).